

Dealing With Diversity: Discourses of Public Elementary School Teachers in a Multicultural Classroom

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Abstract. As our society grows toward the direction of inclusivity and diversity, multicultural education has been emphasized now more than ever. It opens doors and windows of opportunities and possibilities to foster growth and learning in diversified ways. Through a qualitative phenomenological study, the study explored teachers' experiences, strategies, and insights in a multicultural classroom. The study participants were ten (10) male elementary school teachers currently teaching in an elementary school in the East district of Kapalong, Davao del Norte. Extracted narratives from the interview revealed teachers' experiences in multicultural classrooms as the following: students with different socio-economic status, learning styles, and attitudes and values. Meanwhile, the strategies employed by the teachers in dealing with diversity were acknowledging and encouraging every student and diversifying the lesson plan. From these findings, insights were drawn. Practicing cultural sensitivity helps foster respect and acceptance. At the same time, teachers promote the value of learning about different cultures, enabling the class to create harmonious connections with each other and have harmonious relationships amidst diversity. Hence, the study unlocked the perception that diversity would not be a roadblock in creating connections. Instead, it allowed us to broaden our skills and views as a teacher. It was essential to develop an understanding of and respect for students from different backgrounds and cultures. Also, to those people who were different from us in various aspects. One should also make an effort to learn to be able to understand more.

KEY WORDS

1. elementary school teachers 2. multicultural education 3. diversity

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1. Introduction

Every person is born into a culture that provides him with certain patterns of values and behaviors that guide his life. Being aware of different cultures can help an individual better understand a person and adjust to their way of life in order to build a smooth and harmonious relationship. It is through education that one becomes mindful of the appropriate conduct suitable to that culture. Education and culture are connected integrally and intimately since society's cultural pattern specifies its educational pattern. Globalization has shifted the whole world into one borderless society. Jumping from one country to another to find better opportunities abroad has become an ordinary phenomenon in modern times. As societies worldwide become culturally, ethnically, and linguistically diverse, so do the school class-

rooms. Due to globalization, students of different colors, from different races, speaking different languages, and with different beliefs can now be seen inside the four corners of the classroom. Every day, teachers are greeted with different faces of children, each carrying a culture of their own. Teaching learners while having to deal with their diverse backgrounds is very challenging for most teachers. They have a lot to consider inside the classroom to ensure that they are creating a healthy learning environment that promotes inclusivity. They have a crucial role in promoting peace and positive relationships to prevent student conflicts. According to Ballada (2014), teachers must develop care toward their students to help students develop their character and build an encouraging connection with others. They also need to play many roles, such as an adviser, a peacemaker, a listener, and a guidance counselor, which helps the teachers solve cultural indifferences and discrimination, which are two of the problems in a multicultural classroom (Napanan Gadong, 2021). According to Alsubaie (2015), teachers in a multicultural classroom should be provided with knowledge about several cultures of their students as well as their communication style, personal experiences, and learning approaches that are harmonious for all the students in the multicultural classroom. Research shows that stereotypical expectations and cultural differences hinder the quality of relationships among students which sometimes leads to rejection and exclusion for some (Abacioglu et al., 2019). According to Totura, Karver, and Gesten (2014), victimized students, due to cultural differences, are less engaged with school and academic goals compared to their classmates, who are more accepted by everyone. When diverse students are put together inside one classroom, they display different behaviors and create clashes among students. Perso (2004) conducted a study regarding responsive teaching in a multicultural classroom and stressed

that cultural indifferences inside the classroom have been a global problem. To give an example, schools in Malaysia have the challenge of multiethnic and multiracial unification (Malakol-unthu et al., 2010). Although a multicultural classroom brimming with diversity allows teachers and students to have different perspectives and a rich learning opportunity as stated by Banks, Cookson, Gay, Hawley, Irvine, Nieto, Schofield, and Stefan (2001), not all teachers are effective in teaching students in a multicultural classroom in both Western and Asian countries (Kim Jeon, 2017). As a matter of fact, teachers often teach according to their own cultural biases, with teacher preparation programs that are unsuccessful when it comes to incorporating multicultural perspectives into their programs (Allen et al., 2017). Moreover, multicultural education is being affected by the negative attitude of the teachers and school heads toward multiculturalism in some remote schools where there is a high teacher-student ratio (Mapuranga, Bukaliya, 2014). Some teachers are uncomfortable with the growing diversity and Multiculturalism in their workplace (Zembylas, 2010). According to Ramirez (2006), in the research locale, teachers are having a hard time teaching and disciplining students who come from diverse cultures and sub-cultures. These students oftentimes encounter conflicts with their fellow classmates, and because of this, students from different cultures and tribes develop biases (Tawagon, 2008). The biases that developed resulted in physical, verbal-relational, and cyberbullying (Ouano et al., 2013). Hence, teachers' role in addressing these problems in the classroom is given great emphasis. They need to be watchful in dealing with the students' diversity, and they need to employ different strategies that are effective in preventing and solving problems and issues that may arise in a multicultural classroom. However, despite the practical strategies and approaches surrounding cultural awareness and understanding, communicative competence,

and flexibility, there was still no solution that could be administered to make teaching in a multicultural classroom instantaneously easy. Issues must be explored and dealt with the moment they arise, and whenever a successful interaction happens, trust and confidence spiral forward (Witsel, 2003). The teachers' role as the solver of the problem was essential in the classroom because they would have the authority and responsibility to resolve possible conflicts or problems that may arise inside the classroom in relation to discrimination and cultural indifferences (Naparana Gadong, 2021). In Kapalong, Davao del Norte, specifically in the East district, different tribes exist such as the Aetas, Bagobos, Mandaya, and many more. With this diversity in this area, classrooms in elementary are also filled with students carrying their own cultures, beliefs, and practices. With this, it has been observed that elementary teachers are having a hard time teaching in a multicultural classroom and dealing with students' diversity. This study was conceptualized because of this

context. The intent of the researcher in conducting this study was to delve into the lived experiences of elementary school teachers teaching in a multicultural classroom in Kapalong, Davao del Norte, specifically in the East district. How they deal with the students' diversity in a multicultural classroom would also be explored, and educational management insights were drawn from this study. The result of this study would contribute to its body of knowledge, widen the perception of elementary school teachers with regard to multicultural education, and help them improve and develop their effectiveness in teaching and dealing with student diversity inside a multicultural classroom. Elementary school teachers have a crucial role in the lives of their students because they help lay the foundation for creating a new generation where learners are correctly equipped with knowledge as well as a positive attitude to enter the modern world where they are greeted with broader and bigger opportunities as well as challenges.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—This study examined the lived experiences of elementary school teachers in Kapalong, Davao del Norte, who are teaching in a multicultural classroom and discovered their ways of dealing with student diversity. To become efficient and more capable in their field, teachers need to know more about their students' cultures, beliefs, backgrounds, and experiences. Through these pieces of information, they could create a healthy classroom environment that promotes inclusivity where bias and judgment cannot grow. Teachers are said to be the second mothers of the learners, hence, knowing the learners was imperative to build a strong relationship with them. Data was gathered through the lived experiences of elementary school teachers. This would help the researcher formulate meaningful insights to add to the existing body of knowledge about student diversity in a multicultural classroom. Most importantly, it would help the teachers understand more about this topic, which can be of help in improving the teaching and learning process as well as reducing the issues that might arise in a multicultural classroom.

1.2. Research Questions—This study aimed to determine the lived experiences of elementary school teachers in teaching a multicultural classroom and how they deal with students' diversity. This study was conducted, and the researcher sought to answer the following questions:

- (1) What are the lived experiences of elementary school teachers in teaching in a multicultural classroom?
- (2) How do elementary school teachers deal with student diversity in a multicultural classroom?

(3) What educational management insights are drawn from the findings of the study?

1.3. *Definition of Terms*—For a more comprehensive understanding, the following terms were defined operationally: Multicultural education refers to a modern and advanced teaching model that focuses on implementing the princi-

ples of equality and fairness among all students. Cultural sensitivity. It means being aware of cultural differences and similarities without evaluating these as good or bad. Learning styles were described as an idea in education that promotes the idea that every student learns differently.

1.4. *Significant of the Study*—Thus, putting into consideration this cited problem situation and the research questions, the researcher finds it timely to propose this study. This also brought the necessity for the researcher to explore the experiences of elementary school teachers in a multicultural classroom. The researcher hopes that this study was beneficial to identified sectors of the academe. This includes the Department of Education, the school heads/school principals, teachers, and future researchers. The Department of Education would benefit from the study's findings because

they can provide a perspective regarding multicultural education and equip them with new strategies and insights. The school heads/school principals. The study's findings could benefit the school heads/school principals by providing them with an overview of the teachers' situation, experiences, and strategies. The teachers. The study would benefit the teachers by allowing them to learn from the findings on how to address issues and concerns in a multicultural classroom. The future researchers. This would be helpful and an additional contribution to their references for future research in the field of multicultural education.

1.5. *Theoretical Lens*—The study was anchored on James Banks's Multicultural Education Theory (1984). As an expert in multicultural education, Bank inferred that multicultural education is not only the student's but also the educator's responsibility. For educators to incorporate multicultural education into their classroom, curriculum, and teaching style, they must become educated on students' various cultures. This theory will be utilized in the study by scrutinizing teachers' experiences and how they deal with diversity in a multicultural classroom. Additionally, by becoming aware of the different backgrounds that students may bring into the class, the teacher can better contextualize and break down the information being taught. Once an educator is well equipped with multicultural background studies, they can then level the educational field by "giving all stu-

dents more choices about how they will learn choices that are compatible with their cultural styles [so that] none will be unduly advantaged or disadvantaged at the procedural level of learning" (Gay, 1994). Furthermore, incorporating multicultural education may seem exclusive to social science subjects; however, Banks argues that there are numerous opportunities to integrate multicultural education into both math and science curricula. Finding a method in which to introduce multicultural education into a classroom outside of the social sciences and liberal arts requires more effort on the part of the instructor, as the connection and integrations may not be as apparent with Science, Technology, Engineering, and Math education (STEM). Multicultural education advocates the belief that students and their life histories and experiences should be placed at the center of the teaching

and learning process and that pedagogy should occur in a context that is familiar to students and that addresses multiple ways of thinking. Finally, teaching multicultural education is less about a specific subject matter and more about incorporating various backgrounds, histories, cultures, and perspectives into a classroom. A teacher is responsible for promoting inclusivity in the class, making their students feel accepted and welcomed, and, most importantly, providing fair and equal education to every student. The study is further reinforced by Lev Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory (1962), also called social learning theory, which is widely known in sociocultural and educational psychology. This sociocultural theory of development describes learning as a social process and asserts that our social environment dramatically influences our cognitive learning development and mental processes. Our interactions with society and their contributions provide a temporary scaffold until we can internalize our experiences and develop higher levels of thinking. We can then form our consciousness individually, making us both a byproduct and architect of society (Rivera, 2021). In the context of this study, the society pertained in the abovementioned theory could be the classroom. In a multicultural

classroom not, everyone learns the same way and at the same pace, and a learner's experience can vary from another. This is due to cultural diversity, resources, and physical circumstances. When learners participate in societal activities or, in this study, classroom activities and draw from these experiences, they acquire new knowledge and initiatives to help navigate the world around them. Figure 1 presents the conceptual framework of the study. It shows three interconnected variables. The experiences of Lived experiences of the elementary school teachers teaching in a multicultural classroom, a qualitative inquiry that allows researchers and teachers as well as learners to provide the necessary skills, knowledge, and focus on engaging in meaningful inquiry about their professional practice would enhance this practice and effect positive changes concerning the Ways of elementary school teachers in dealing student diversity. There was a genuine concern, as could be viewed with the first circle, which interlinks to the second circle; however, the center of the two circles determines that there was a way of exploring the Insights gained from the experiences of the elementary school teachers teaching in a multicultural classroom.

2. Methodology

This chapter of the study presents the method, research participants, data collection, role of the researcher, data analysis, trustworthiness of the study, and ethical considerations. Exploring facts and knowledge in this study necessitates the consequent design and implementation, as elaborated in this chapter. The three most common qualitative methods are participant observation, in-depth interviews, and focus groups. Each method was particularly suited for obtaining a specific type of data. Participant observation was appropriate for collecting data on naturally occurring behaviors in their usual contexts. In-depth Interviews (IDI) were optimal for collecting data on individuals' personal histories, perspectives, and experiences, particularly when sensitive topics are being explored. Patton (2002) defined phenomenology as an inquiry that asks the question, "What is the structure and essence of the experience of his phenomenon for these people?" The goal of this research worked well with this definition in trying to unfold the lived experiences of elementary teachers who are teaching in a multicultural while dealing with student diversity. Giorgi (2007) cautioned researchers to be prepared for an investigation greater in depth and breadth than the

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

offered description implied. He suggested the information be viewed as only the tip of the iceberg.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The philosophical assumption was a framework used to collect, analyze, and interpret the data collected in a specific field of study. It establishes the background used for the coming conclusions and decisions. Typical philosophical assumptions have different types and are elaborated on below. Good research – undertaking the selection of the topic, problem, or area of interest, as well as the paradigm. Stanage (1987) traces ‘paradigm’ back to its Greek (paradigm) and Latin origins (paradigm) meaning pattern, model, or example among examples, an exemplar or model to follow according to which design actions are taken. Differently stated, a paradigm was an act of submitting to a view. This view was supported by Denzin and Lincoln (2000), who defend a research paradigm as a “basic set of beliefs that guide action,” dealing with first principles, “ultimates” or the researcher’s worldview or philosophy. Ontology. This part of the research pertains to how the issue relates to the nature of reality. According to Creswell (2012), the reality is subjective and multiple as seen by participants in the study. The ontological issue addresses the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher. The reality was constructed by individuals involved in the research situation. Thus, multiple realities exist, such as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals being investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. In this study, the lived experiences of elementary school teachers teaching in a multicultural classroom are discussed. How they deal with student diversity would also be explored in the hopes that the researcher can gain meaningful insights from this study. In this study, the researcher relied on the voices and interpretations of the participants through extensive quotes and themes that reflected their words and provided evidence of different perspectives. The answers of the participants to the study were coded and analyzed to build and construct the commonality and discreteness of responses. It was made sure that the responses of the participants were carefully coded to ensure the reliability of the result. The researcher upheld the authenticity of the responses and precluded from making personal bias as the study progressed. Epistemology. This refers to the awareness of how knowledge claims are justified by staying as close to the participants as possible during the study to obtain firsthand information. Guba and Lincoln, as cited by Creswell (2012), state that on the epistemological assumption, the researcher attempted to lessen the distance between himself or herself from the participants. He suggests that being a researcher he or she collaborates, spends time in the field with participants, and becomes an ‘insider’. Based on Davidson (2000) and Jones (2006), researchers identified phenomenology with the use of thematic analysis as the best means for this type of study. In this regard, individual researchers “hold explicit belief”. This study intends to delve deeper into the lived experiences of elementary school teachers teaching in a multicultural classroom in Kapalong, Davao del Norte, based on the guidelines set by DepEd and the Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF). It was assured that there was an establishment of close interaction with the participants to gain direct information that would shed light on the knowledge behind the inquiry, particularly on the lived experiences of elementary school teachers teaching in a multicultural classroom and how they deal with student diversity. Axiology. It refers to the role of values in research. Creswell (2012) avers that the role of values in a study was significant. Axiology suggests that the researcher openly discusses values that shape the narrative and includes their interpretation in conjunction with the interpretation of par-

participants. Upholding the dignity and value of every detail of information obtained from the participants was ensured by the researcher. The researcher understands the personal and value-laden nature of the information gathered from the study. Therefore, the researcher preserved the merit of the participants' answers and carefully interpreted the answers in the light of the participants' interpretation. Rhetoric. It means reporting what reality was through the eyes of

2.2. Qualitative Assumptions—The methodology was different from the method. The methodology was a creative and responsive approach to understanding questions and subject matter, while the method refers to the exact knowledge and procedure (Gerodias, 2013). In this study, the lived experiences of elementary school teachers teaching in a multicultural classroom and how they deal with student diversity in Kapalong, Davao del Norte, were gathered through an In-Depth Interview (IDI) and Focus Group Discussion (FGD) and the coping mechanisms were extracted from the participants. The researcher's drive to know the deeper meaning of the experiences in multicultural classrooms of elementary school teachers and their ways of dealing with student diversity became the basis for doing qualitative research, a means by which Kalof and Dietz (2008), as cited from Gerodias (2013) considered helpful in looking for "meanings and motivations that underline cultural symbols, personal experiences, and phenomena". By using phenomenology, this need was hoped to be addressed by bringing the lived experiences of elementary school teachers with regard to student diversity in a multicultural

2.3. Design and Procedure—This study employed a qualitative approach to research, specifically a phenomenological research de-

the research participants. This was important because it meant that the research would report objectively on what was observed and heard from the participants. The research used personal voice and qualitative terms and limited definitions. In the context of the study, the researcher used the first person to elucidate the lived experiences of elementary school teachers teaching in a multicultural classroom and dealing with student diversity.

classroom in a manner that, as David (2005) wrote, the themes, symbols, and meaning of the experiences presented. Phenomenological research was based on two premises. The first was that experience was a valid, rich, and rewarding source of knowledge. According to Becker (1992), as cited in Morrissey and Higgs (2006), that experience is a source of knowledge and shapes one's behavior. From the definition, human experience was viewed as a cornerstone of knowledge about human phenomena and not as an unreliable source. The second premise of phenomenological research lies in the view that the everyday world is a valuable and productive source of knowledge, and that we can learn much about ourselves and reap key insights into the nature of an event by analyzing how it occurs in our daily lives (Morrissey Higgs, 2006). By doing phenomenology which was concerned with the "what" and the "how" (Moustakas, 2000), the lived experiences of elementary school teachers teaching in a multicultural classroom and dealing with student diversity were explored and educational management insights gained were the basis for the possible future research and policy analysis in relation to this research.

sign. According to Creswell, (2012), phenomenology was an approach to qualitative research that focused on the commonality of lived

experiences within a particular group. The fundamental goal of the approach was to arrive at a description of the nature of the particular phenomenon. Typically, interviews were conducted with a group of individuals who have first-hand knowledge of an event, situation, or experience. Other forms of data, such as documents, observations, and art, were also used. The data were read and reread and were culled for phrases and themes that were grouped into clusters of meanings. Through this process, the researcher was able to construct the universal meaning of the event, situation, or experience and arrive at a more profound understanding of the phenomenon. Moreover, Maxwell (2013) also added that with its roots in philosophy, psychology, and education, phenomenology attempts to extract the purest, untainted data. In some interpretations of the approach, the researcher used bracketing to document personal experiences with the subject to help remove him or her from the process. One method of bracketing is taking notes. According to Corbetta (2003), the phenomenological research design was a qualitative type of research for which interviews provide an in-depth method that can grant access to deep knowledge and explanations and help grasp the subjects' perspective. Creswell (2012) also claimed that interviews were primarily done in qualitative research and occur when researchers ask one or more participants general, open-ended questions and record their answers. Often audio tapes were utilized to allow more consistent transcription. Interviews are also useful to follow up with individual respondents after questionnaires, such as to further investigate their responses. In qualitative research, interviews were used to pursue the meanings of central themes in the world of their subjects. The main task in doing interviews was to understand the meaning of what the interviewees said (McNamara, 1999). Withal, based on the statements of Quad (2016), the researcher transcribed and typed the data into a computer

file, in order to analyze it after interviewing. Interviews particularly be useful for uncovering the story behind a participant's experiences and pursuing in-depth information about a topic. The researcher collected data, typically via long interviews, from individuals who have experienced the phenomenon under investigation. Next, the data analysis involved triangulation that extracted significant statements from the transcribed interviews. The significant statements were transformed into clusters of meanings according to how each statement fell under specific psychological and phenomenological concepts. Moreover, these transformations were tied up together to make a general description of the experience, both the textural description of what was experienced and the structural description of how it was experienced. The researcher incorporated his or her personal meaning of the experiences here. Finally, the report was written such that readers understand better the essential, invariant structure of the essence of the experience. Conversely, several challenges have been pointed out. The researcher required a solid grounding in the philosophical guidelines of phenomenology. The subjects selected for the study were individuals who had actually experienced the phenomenon. The researcher needed to bracket his or her own experiences and observations, which was difficult. The researcher also needed to decide how and when his or her personal observations would be incorporated into the study. Epistemologically, phenomenological approaches were based on the paradigm of personal knowledge and subjectivity and emphasized the importance of personal perspective and interpretation. As such, they were powerful tools for understanding subjective experience, gaining insights into people's motivations and actions, and cutting through the cluster of taken-for-granted assumptions and conventional wisdom. Since the focus of this study was to examine the elementary school teachers' lived experiences teaching in a multicultural class-

room while dealing with student diversity and educational insights gained from the findings of the study, the researcher would intend to employ

2.4. Research Participants—Qualitative analyses typically require a smaller sample size than the quantitative analyses. Qualitative sample sizes should be large enough to obtain feedback for most or all perceptions. Obtaining most or all of the perceptions would lead to the attainment of saturation. Saturation occurs when adding more participants to the study does not result in additional perspectives or information. Glaser and Strauss (1967) recommend the concept of saturation for achieving an appropriate sample size in qualitative studies. For phenomenological studies, Creswell (1998) recommends five (5) to twenty-five (25), and Morse (1994) suggests at least six (6). There are no specific rules when determining the appropriate

2.5. Ethical Considerations—Ethical considerations are significant in the design of this research study. The researcher needed to consider several ethical issues regarding the research participant in this fieldwork. Ethical considerations can be specified as one of the most important parts of the research. The researcher needs to adhere to promote the aims of the research by imparting authentic knowledge and truth and preventing errors. Social Value. The research was very essential to society. In this study, the social value was focused on the lived experiences of elementary school teachers teaching in a multicultural classroom and how they deal with student diversity. This study was specifically conducted among elementary school teachers in Kapalong, Davao del Norte. This study also served as a basis for the higher authorities to create more programs and resolutions from which elementary school teachers teach-

the phenomenology type of qualitative method research.

sample size in qualitative research. Qualitative sample size may best be determined by the time allotted, resources available, and study objectives (Patton, 1990). The participants of this study were Ten (10) elementary school teachers from Kapalong, Davao Del Norte, specifically in the East district. The participants were chosen based on the following criteria: (1) elementary school teachers and (2) teaching in a multicultural classroom. The researcher utilized the purposive sampling design since the participants were chosen based on the criteria or purpose of the study (Creswell, 2014). It was also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling. The selection of the participants was purposefully done to ensure that the findings would be authentic (Marshall, 1996).

ing in a multicultural classroom could benefit. Thus, the social problem that pushes the interest of the researcher is the lived experiences of elementary school teachers teaching in a multicultural classroom as well as how they deal with student diversity. Informed Consent. In the conduct and practice of this study, the Treaty Principle of Participation, as cited by McLeod (2009), was adhered to. The invitation to the participants ensured that their participation in the research was completely voluntary in nature and was based on the understanding of adequate information. The recruitment and selection of participants are lodged in the appendices of this study. Gaining the trust and support of research participants was critical to informed and ethical academic inquiry and phenomenological research (Walker, 2007 as cited by Pillerin, 2012). All participants were given an informed consent form before scheduling the interviews

and participating in the phenomenological research process. Each participant was required to provide a signed personal acknowledgment, consent, and an indication of a willingness to participate in the study release. The purpose of the informed consent letter was to introduce the research effort, provide contact information, articulate the study's intent, request voluntary participation by the recipients, and anticipate the information the informants were expected to provide. All participants were required to sign and return the letter of consent to the researcher before participating in the research.

Vulnerability of Research Participants. The participants of this study were capable of answering the research instrument, for they are all professional teachers in elementary schools. Thus, the researcher assured them that as the researcher, he or she can easily be reached through the contact number and address in case there are some clarifications or questions about the study.

Risks, Benefits, and Safety. The recruitment of the respondents was free of coercion, undue influence, or inducement. Moreover, respondents were provided with the contact numbers of the chair of the panel or panel members in case they had queries related to the study. Furthermore, in the event that respondents would experience potential discomfort and inconvenience while answering the questions, they were not compelling to participate in any manner. Further, the researcher ensured that the respondents were safe during the survey and interview. Thus, the questionnaire was distributed in a safe venue and administered at a convenient time. The dominant concern of this study was the Treaty Principle of Protection, as reflected in the respect for the rights of privacy and confidentiality, and minimization of risk. This was done by assigning pseudonyms for each informant so as not to disclose their identity. The possibility of a degree of risk inherent to this was minimized by taking all reasonable steps to guarantee participant confidentiality. Privacy and

Confidentiality of Information. This study observed the Data Privacy Act of 2002 to ensure that the data cannot be traced back to their real sources to protect participants' identities. Thus, utmost care was taken to ensure the anonymity of the data sources. Hence, any printed output that was carried out from this study was kept in anonymity. Furthermore, all the issues were given consideration so that there would be no conflict of interest between the researcher and the respondents. Any misleading information and representation of primary data findings in a biased way must be avoided.

Justice. The respondents were informed of the researcher's role and their corresponding role during data gathering. They were briefed that they have to give their complete honesty in answering the survey questions and additionally, any type of communication in relation to the research should be done with honesty. Similarly, they were informed that they were the ones to benefit first from the results of the study.

Transparency. The results of the study were accessed by the respondents and heads of the participating schools because the information is available and will be placed on CDs or other storage devices, which can be requested from the researcher. In addition, by learning from the study's results, classroom teachers were aware of the significance of the study and its contribution to their well-being. Further, each participant was advised that they have the right to withdraw their information at any time up to the completion of the data collection process and that they can be requested and allowed to verify their transcript after the interview is carried out. This allowed the participants to amend or remove any information they felt might identify them. The researcher reserved the right to employ the use of pseudonyms and change names and/or non-significant dates in the interest of protecting the identity of the participant in all subsequent data analysis and reporting.

Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher ensured that he or

she possessed the needed qualifications to conduct the study. The researcher should have completed the academic requirements and passed the comprehensive examination before thesis writing, which was the last requirement to obtain the master's degree. The researcher should also be qualified to conduct the study physically, mentally, emotionally, and financially. In addition, the advisee-adviser tandem ensured that the study would reach its completion. Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher strived to ensure that the study could be completed successfully in the specified time and that he or she was equipped with the necessary resources. Likewise, the technical committee helped enhance the paper by giving suggestions and recommendations for improving the study. Also, the researcher ensured that he or she had enough funds to continue and finish the research. Thus, this study was hoped to be completed within the target time. Community Involvement. The

researcher showed respect for the respondents' local traditions, culture, and views in this study. Moreover, this study did not involve any use of deceit in any stage of its implementation, specifically, in the recruitment of the participants, or methods of data collection. Furthermore, the researcher necessarily expressed great pleasure for the wholehearted participation of the interviewees in the conduct of the study. Plagiarism and Fabrication as the researcher. The researcher respected other works by properly citing the author and rewriting what someone else has said his or her own way. The researcher also used quotes to indicate that the text had been taken from another paper. Similarly, the researcher assured that honesty was present in working on the manuscript and no intentional misrepresentation and making up of data or results was included, or purposefully put forward conclusions that are not accurate.

2.6. Role of the Researcher—The researcher has a responsibility to uncover, transfer, and exploit knowledge for the benefit of educational institutions. To do so, the researcher takes up the following roles in the course of the study: Facilitator and Promoter of Unbiased Research. The researcher interviews the participants and guides them in the process. The researcher interprets ideas and responses based on existing literature and related studies and not on the researcher's knowledge, thoughts, and feelings to avoid the intrusion of bias. Expert in qualitative methods. The researcher implements the qualitative method correctly. To do so, the researcher assesses himself and seeks help from the research adviser and other professionals. These help him demonstrate competence in explaining the study without biasing the participants, conducting interviews according to the design, making appropriate field observations, selecting appropriate artifacts, images, and journal por-

tions, and employing Environmental Triangulation and Thematic Content Analysis precisely. Collector and Keeper of data. The researcher ensures different ways of making a record of what was said and done during the interview and Focus Group Discussion, such as taking handwritten notes or audio and video recording. The recordings were transcribed verbatim before data analysis could begin. Records done by the researcher were adequately secured as they contained sensitive information and were relevant to the research. However, when the data were being collected, the researcher's primary responsibility was to safeguard participants and their data. Mechanisms for safeguarding must be clearly articulated to participants and approved by a relevant research ethics review board before the research begins. Data analyst. The researcher sees the phenomenon or problem from the participants' perspective by interpreting data, transcribing and checking,

reading between the lines, coding, and theming. The researcher ensures that the findings are true to the participants and that their voices are heard. Organizer and presenter of data. The researcher presents the problem and the related works of literature and studies that support it. The study's findings were presented by research

questions – stating the results for each one by using themes to show how the research questions were answered in the study. Moreover, the researcher gives future directions and implications of the study for improving educational policy and practices.

2.7. Data Collection—The following is the step-by-step process of gathering the data needed. Securing endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School. In the last week of May 2023, the researcher asked for an endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School of Rizal Memorial Colleges as one of the documents needed for submission to the office of the Schools Division Superintendent to ask permission to conduct the study. Asking permission from the Schools Division Superintendent. The researcher asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent in the first week of June 2023 to conduct the study in the identified school. The researcher would send a letter addressed to the Schools Division Superintendent with the attached Chapters 1 and 2 together with the research instrument, which explains the objectives of the study and the identification of the participants. The researcher would wait for the SDS's response before conducting it. Asking for permission from the school heads. After securing the approval of the SDS, the researcher sent letters to the principals of the schools in the third week of June 2023, explaining the study to be conducted in their schools. Obtaining consent from the participants. During the fourth week of June 2023, the researcher asked permission from the participants. They were formally

oriented about the study and the process they would undergo as participants. Conducting the interview. In the same week, the researcher conducted an in-depth interview using the interview questionnaire. The profile of the participants was taken, notes were jotted down, and conversations were recorded using a sound recorder for ease of transcription. The researcher carefully listened and responded actively during the interviews. Transcribing the responses of the interviewees. On the last week of June 2023, the researcher transcribed the responses of the interviewees precisely by recalling their answers from the sound recorder. Since some of the participants used their vernacular language, the researcher translated it into English. Data Coding and Thematic Content Analysis. After the transcription, the data will then be categorized and coded. Then, themes were extracted, and individual participant data were compared and contrasted. The researcher then conducted a second round of interviews (FGD) to corroborate any data that needed further explanation and input from the participants; additional information gathered was examined thoroughly and integrated into the existing body of data. After this, data were compared and contrasted between the participants to develop patterns and trends.

2.8. Data Analysis—In this study, thematic analysis was utilized to analyze the gathered data. The researcher analyzed the answers of the participants from the conducted inter-

views using Creswell's Model, specifically the identifying of themes approach. According to Creswell (2012), themes in qualitative research are similar codes aggregated together to form a

major idea in the database. Familiarization with the data was common to all forms of qualitative analysis. The researcher immersed herself in and became intimately familiar with the data, reading and re-reading it and noting any initial analytic observations. Coding was also a common element of many approaches to qualitative analysis, involving generating pithy labels for essential features of the data relevant to the (broad) research question guiding the analysis. Coding was not simply a data reduction method but also an analytic process, so codes capture both a semantic and conceptual reading of the data. The researcher coded every data item and ended this phase by collating all their codes and relevant data extracts. Searching for themes was a coherent and meaningful pattern in the data relevant to the research question. The researcher ended this phase by collating all the coded data relevant to each theme. Reviewing themes. The researcher reflected on whether the themes told a convincing and compelling story about the data and began to define the nature of each theme and the relationship between the themes. Thematic Content Analysis was employed by the researcher for these. Thematic Content Analysis was a descriptive presentation of qualitative data in which a detailed analysis of each theme was made by identifying the 'essence' of each theme and construct-

ing a concise, punchy, and informative name for each theme (Andersen, 2013). In addition, to enhance validity and create a more in-depth picture of the phenomenon, the researcher employed environmental triangulation. It was a technique to analyze the same study's results using different data collection methods. The key was identifying which environmental factors might influence the information received during the study. These environmental factors were changed to see if the findings were the same across the settings (David, 2015). This type of triangulation uses different settings, locations, and other factors, such as the time, day, and season of the study. The idea was to determine which factors influence the information received; these factors were then changed to see if the findings were the same. Validity can be established if the findings remain unaltered under varying environmental factors (Naeem, 2019). In this study, such triangulation was used considering that the requirement, as mentioned, was the use of environmental triangulation best suited to the environment of the research being conducted. Writing-up involves weaving together the analytic narrative and data extracts to tell the reader a coherent and persuasive story about the data and contextualizing it concerning existing literature.

2.9. Framework of Analysis—The framework analysis of this research was flexible to allow the researcher to either collect all the data and then analyze it or do data analysis during the collection process. In the analysis stage, the gathered data was sifted, charted, and sorted by key issues and themes. This involves a five-step process: (1) familiarization, (2) identifying a thematic framework, (3) indexing, (4) charting, and (5) mapping and interpretation (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). Familiarization refers to the process during which the

researcher becomes familiarized with the transcripts of the data collected (i.e., interview or focus group transcripts, observation, or field notes) and gains an overview of the collected data (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). In other words, the researcher becomes immersed in the data by listening to audiotapes, studying the field, or reading the transcripts. Throughout this process, the researcher becomes aware of critical ideas and recurrent themes and makes a note of them. Due to the sheer volume of data that can be collected in qualitative research, the re-

searcher may not be able to review all of the material. Thus, a selection of the data set would be utilized. The selection would depend on several aspects of the data collection process. For example, the mix of methods used (e.g., interviews, documents, observations), The second stage, identifying a thematic framework, occurs after familiarization, when the researcher recognizes emerging themes or issues in the data set. These emerging themes or issues may have arisen from a priori themes; however, at this stage, the researcher must allow the data to dictate the themes and issues. To achieve this end, the researcher uses the notes taken during the familiarization stage. The key issues, concepts, and themes that have been expressed by the participants now form the basis of a thematic framework that can be used to filter and classify the data (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). Indexing means identifying portions or sections of the data that correspond to a particular theme. This process is applied to all the textual data that has been gathered (e.g., transcripts of interviews). For

2.10. Trustworthiness of the Study—Trustworthiness was all about establishing credibility, transferability, confirmability, and dependability. In a qualitative study, trustworthiness is very important because the results and findings of the research study would depend on the researcher's process of conducting it. The trustworthiness of a research study was important for evaluating its worth. Due to the nature of the qualitative study, honesty in all the data and details is required. Trustworthiness makes the researcher's study worthy to read, share, and be proud of. Credibility measured how confident the qualitative researcher was in the truth of the research study's findings. The researcher in this study believed that honesty in everything you do is essential to attaining worthwhile success. The researcher has no derogatory records or administrative issues that ruin her integrity. Lincoln

the sake of convenience, Ritchie and Spencer (1994) recommend that a numerical system be used for the indexing references and annotated in the margin beside the text. Qualitative data analysis tools are ideal for such a task. The final stage, mapping, and interpretation, involves the analysis of the key characteristics as laid out in the charts. This analysis should be able to provide a schematic diagram of the event/phenomenon, thus guiding the researcher in their interpretation of the data set. At this point, the researcher was cognizant of the objectives of qualitative analysis: "defining concepts, mapping range and nature of phenomena, creating typologies, finding associations, providing explanations, and developing strategies" (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). Once again, these concepts, technologies, and associations are reflective of the participant. Therefore, any strategy or recommendations made by the researcher echo the true attitudes, beliefs, and values of the participants.

and Guba (1985) stated that credibility refers to the idea of internal consistency, where the main issue was "how we ensure rigor in the research process and how we communicate to others that we have done so." Transferability is how the qualitative researcher demonstrates that the research study's findings apply to other contexts. In this case, "other contexts" can mean similar situations, similar populations, and similar phenomena. The researcher has already studied the effects of using a graphic organizer as a strategy for teaching reading comprehension. Using graphic organizers as a strategy for teaching reading comprehension is effective in the domains of analysis and creation. The researcher was interested in the student's perspective on using this strategy. Gasson (2004) emphasizes transferability as the extent to which the reader can provide a generalization of the study based

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

on his own context and can address the core issue of “how far a researcher may make claims for a general application of the theory.” Confirmability was the degree of neutrality in the research study’s findings. In other words, this means that the findings are based on participants’ responses and not the researcher’s potential bias or personal motivations. This involves ensuring that researcher bias does not skew the interpretation of what the research participants said to fit a particular narrative. The information used in the audit trail in this situation is thoughtfully recorded by the researcher, which highlights every step of data analysis that was made in order to provide a rationale for the decisions made. This helps establish that the research study’s findings accurately portray participants’ responses. Gasson (2004) states that confirmability was based on the acknowledgment that research is never objective. Dependability was

the extent to which other researchers could repeat the study and ensure that the findings were consistent. In other words, if a person wanted to replicate your study, they should have enough information from your research report to do so and obtain similar findings as your study did. A qualitative researcher used an inquiry audit to establish dependability, which requires an outside person to review and examine the research process and the data analysis to ensure that the findings are consistent and can be repeated. In this component, using a database was very important in backing up information collected and noting changes for all types of research studies. All the data collected were kept correctly for future use as references. Gasson (2004) stated that dependability deals with the core issue that “how a study was conducted should be consistent across time, researchers, and analysis techniques.”

3. Results and Discussion

This part of the study dealt with the research questions and their answers based on the responses of the participants. The study explored the discourses of elementary school teachers regarding teaching in a multicultural classroom.

3.1. The experiences of elementary school teachers in a multicultural classroom—The system of education has evolved for the betterment and enrichment of the delivery of learning to everyone everywhere with varied cultures and backgrounds. Nowadays, teachers are greeted by students coming from different cultures. The

21st century opens doors and windows for inclusivity, making classrooms more diverse. However, although it indicates a positive message, it poses challenges on the part of the teachers. Since there is a variety of students, teachers should come up with ways that cater to everyone. The study discovered the experiences of elementary teachers in a multicultural classroom.

3.1.1. Different socio-economic status—In a class as diverse as a multicultural classroom, differences among students will surface. Among those are the differences in socio-economic status. Students come from different backgrounds. Some have enough, others have a lot, and some almost have nothing. As the teachers narrated in the interview, one aspect

that differentiates the students in the classroom is their economic status, and this can also hinder the students’ learning. The American Psychologist Association (2017) supports the narratives of the participants. According to them, the differences in students’ socio-economic status (SES) are one of the experiences a teacher may encounter in a multicultural class. These

differences bring about various experiences like students' academic progress, how motivated they are, how prepared they are for the class, and what resources they lack. All of these simmers down to their SES and what a teacher can do to provide equal opportunities for everyone. Additionally, socioeconomic status affects everyone in different ways, whether from higher, lower, or in-between statuses. Everyone fits into a category. Socioeconomic status may affect the quality of life, attributes, opportunities, and privileges offered to people. Those from lower socio-economic status are more vulnerable to suffering from these consequences and rarely get the chance to reap the benefits, sometimes propelling their children into the same cycle. Most of the teachers' narratives regarding the existence of different socio-economic status focus on students who come from low socio-economic backgrounds, Hayes (2019), stated in her study these students tend to have more problems at home, which can lead to it affecting their behavior at school. Hayes (2019) also inferred that students from low-income backgrounds have different needs than students from higher-income backgrounds as they have access to fewer resources, they are more stressed and are sick more often, and home provides less emotional support, and intellectual stimulation. The American Psychologist Association (2017) further reinforces the abovementioned view. There are many comparisons between children from low socioeconomic statuses and high socioeconomic statuses. Students from low SES develop academic skills slower, which is related to poor cognitive development, language, memory, socioemotional processing, and poor income and health in adulthood. Not only do the students develop slower, but the resources provided by the school are not adequate, which impacts their academic progress. The aforementioned authors and the teacher participants do share some perspectives regarding students' economic standing. Their status at home can

affect how they learn at school. For students who come from low socio-economic status, this could be a roadblock in their learning at school. A participant also mentioned how some students encounter problems with access to various resources. Hayes (2019) agreed with that. According to him, not all students have access to the same resources, such as the Internet or coloring materials. For instance, children's literacy environment in the home affects how they develop fundamental skills of reading acquisition, such as phonological awareness, vocabulary, and oral language. Students from low SES are less likely to have the fundamental skills to develop at the rate they should compared to their high SES counterparts, caused by the lack of books owned at home, parental distress, less access to learning material and experiences, or lack of a positive literacy environment. It is important to note that, as educators, we need to develop personal, caring relationships with students to develop trust and transparency. Through this, teachers will have a better understanding of the child's home life and can relate to their students from an empathetic, equitable, equal, or just position and provide resources or solutions to the students and their families (Taylor, n.d). It was further supported by Yale (2017). He stated that with challenges come opportunities to overcome these differences that occur in a multicultural classroom. Opportunities present themselves in many ways to address the concern of SES in the classroom. Starting on the first day of class, it is important for the educator to set classroom rules for behavior emphasizing respect, honesty, and an open-door policy for students. This is a time and place to set ground rules regarding acceptance and civility, though also begin building an open and trusting relationship with students – however, it is not probable for students to open up freely about difficult conversations as there has been no trust or sense of safety developed amongst classmates and teacher-student. Furthermore,

he also added that teachers should also present themselves as available to have open discussions with students anytime but should also require one-on-one check-ins with all students to discuss learning progress and personalize strategies for their improvement. Throughout the term or year, teachers are able to take their time and examine the requirements of assessments and evaluations, clearly state what is required of them, and provide resources and instruction. Other examples of opportunities to address SES as mentioned by Hayes (2019), could be reading a book and having an opening discussion, allowing students to open up in different ways, and exposing students to multiple viewpoints. It is important to integrate content with diverse perspectives and representation by including books, authors, videos, and examples, as this helps students recognize the content through a personal connection. However, according to Taylor (n.d.), regardless of a student's SES, all students have the same rights and responsibilities, even though some may require extra care and support. It is the teachers' role to teach, support, and meet the needs of all students. Whatever a student's upbringing in a multicultural class, the teachers must see them all with fair eyes and provide a fair education to everyone in the class. It is important to note that, as educators, we need to develop personal, caring relationships with students to develop trust and transparency. Through this, teachers will have a better understanding of the child's home life and can relate to their students from an empathetic, equitable, equal, or just position and provide resources or solutions to the students and their families (Taylor, n.d). But with challenges come opportunities to overcome these differences that occur in a multicultural classroom. Opportunities present themselves in many ways to address the concern of SES in the classroom. Starting on the first day of class, it is important for the educator to set classroom rules for behavior emphasizing respect, honesty, and an open-door policy for

students (Yale, 2017). This is a time and place to set ground rules regarding acceptance and civility, though also begin building an open and trusting relationship with students. However, it is not probable for students to open up freely about difficult conversations as there has been no trust or sense of safety developed between classmates and teacher-student. Yale (2017) also added that teachers should also present themselves as available to have open discussions with students anytime but should also require one-on-one check-ins with all students to discuss learning progress and personalize strategies for their improvement. Throughout the term or year, teachers can take their time and examine the requirements of assessments and evaluations, clearly state what is required of them, and provide resources and instruction. However, another approach to targeting lower SES students would be to have an open discussion about what the students reckon is reasonable considering the resources they have available. This also ensures that students have a voice, a choice, and that it matters. In short, they are given autonomy in their class regarding their education, whereas not many lower SES students have that opportunity at home. Other examples of opportunities to address SES, as mentioned by Hayes (2019), could be reading a book and having an opening discussion, allowing students to open up in different ways, and exposing students to multiple viewpoints. It is important to integrate content with diverse perspectives and representation by including books, authors, videos, and examples, as this helps students recognize the content through a personal connection. Staying connected to the world around us with current and relevant information allows teachers to improve teaching and learning, as well as continuing their professional development, and involving parents. all contribute to strategies for discussing and tackling socioeconomic inequalities in the classroom as these are all aids to better teach and bring attention to

topics pertaining to diversity. Having a multicultural approach to teaching and learning allows students to become active seekers and produc-

3.1.2. Various learning styles—Every single child in this enormously diverse and ever-evolving system has the inherent power to provide an invaluable resource for others. Every single child in this ever-evolving system is unique and each has their own set of needs and learning styles. Inclusivity is ideal yet in a way, challenging. In a multicultural class, it is important to note that students come into the class with different learning styles. It is now the teachers' task to make sure that the students learn in the best way they can. In line with the participants' responses both in the in-depth interview and focus group discussion, Grand Canyon University (2020) stated that learning styles are widely accepted in education as a way to promote the idea that every student learns differently. Learning styles are not a prescription for teaching students, but they help a teacher recognize the preferential way in which a student processes and retains information. Moreover, about learning styles, Egbo (2015) points out that every student has a preferred learning style and that there is no one correct way to learn—or, by extension, teach—a language. There is no one-size-fits-all when it comes to classroom instruction. Each student has their own set of learning styles and needs. Students come not in boxes, but in different shapes and sizes. The same study also noted that language learners from different countries may have different pre-

3.1.3. Differences in attitude and values—In a multicultural classroom, teachers are greeted by students who come from vast backgrounds and have diverse upbringings. There is a high chance that they differ in more ways than one. Included in the list are their attitudes and values. They tend to have different behaviors and different perspectives, as well as val-

ers of knowledge, learning more, and faster, and developing a higher curiosity.

ferred learning styles. Further, several personality traits, including introversion and extroversion, anxiety, self-esteem, empathy, dominance, talkativeness, and responsiveness, have been studied in connection with language learning. According to Jones and Young (2013), a person from a minority group learning a majority group language may have different attitudes and motivations than a person from a majority group learning a minority language. Learners from some ethnic groups, perhaps more than others, may be more willing to learn a language based on how they are perceived or feel they are perceived in the community. Somani (2022) explained how teachers can address these differences. According to him, teachers can encourage equitable learning by being aware of their students' varied learning styles, which are influenced by their backgrounds. They can also encourage students to learn from each other's experiences and ask questions that promote understanding. With our society's increasing inclusivity, classrooms are becoming more diverse. A famous adage states that every child is unique, and so are their learning styles. They learn differently. However, a teacher cannot tailor a lesson to suit one and every student's diverse learning styles, especially if they come from diverse backgrounds. However, finding common ground and identifying how students learn best could be a piece of cake for teachers.

ues in life. In line with the participants' narratives, teachers throughout the education system preach respect: respect for the materials in the classroom, respect for the teacher, the staff, and, most importantly, each other. Alan, Ertac, and Mumcu (2018) support their statements aforementioned responses of teachers. In their study, they found that students can struggle with re-

specting each other due to a misunderstanding of their values. If not exposed to diversity, how to respect others' values comes from imitation of their parents, or the media they consume, both of which can be extremely offensive due to outdated terminology and appropriateness. Intuitively this makes sense, when students are aware of why their classmates act or think the way they do, instead of getting bullied they can be praised, raising confidence levels and willingness to try new things as well as putting themselves out there. Consequently, it is deemed vital for an educator to incorporate the teaching of different cultural values into lessons as often as possible. This can be done seamlessly through many subjects such as language, dance, art, music, and more. Soner and Munevver (2019), agree with this and expressed that when teachers of young students teach with respect to the values of different cultures, it was found that stu-

dents of different cultures gained equal access to opportunities, and education in the school was enhanced. In connection to that, the American University School of Education (2020) suggests four ways of implementing multicultural education in the classroom to help make students aware of the different values their classmates may hold, as outlined in the table below. Multicultural education offers a great opportunity for students to learn how they are similar and unique from one another. Throughout the education system, teachers will preach respect. Respect the materials in the classroom, respect the teacher, the staff, and most importantly, each other. Intuitively, this makes sense. When students are aware of why their classmates act or think the way they do, they can be praised instead of bullied, raising their confidence levels and willingness to try new things and put themselves out there.

3.2. Dealing with diversity in a multicultural classroom—In our increasingly diverse and multicultural society, now more than ever, it is important for teachers to incorporate culturally responsive instruction in the classroom – whether teaching elementary school, middle

school, or high school students. There are several ways to address diversity in a classroom. It will help the students feel welcome and accepted. These strategies will encourage all students' cultural awareness, enhance each student's sense of identity, and foster inclusion in the classroom community.

3.2.1. Acknowledging and encouraging every student—It is important that in a classroom, every student feels welcomed, accepted, and recognized. No matter the differences that divide them, teachers should build bridges so everyone can participate and learn together. Drexel University supports the participants' statements. According to them, when appropriate, teachers should encourage students to research and learn about their own ethnic and cultural backgrounds. This allows them to better understand their own culture as well as the differences and nuances with their peers. As a bonus, this can

be a great icebreaker assignment, allowing students to give presentations about their family traditions and culture to help expose the class to concepts outside of their own familiar comfort zone. Hence, the statements of the participants wherein they expressed how much they were encouraged to speak about their culture and background coincide with the study stated. Moreover, acknowledging these differences and creating a safe space for discussion helps promote understanding in the classroom and beyond. Also, as you encourage students to learn about their diverse backgrounds, remember to

Fig. 3. The Lived Experiences of Elementary School Teachers in a Multicultural Classroom

take the time to highlight what's offensive and the distinction between cultural celebration and appropriation. Learning how to talk about other cultures in a respectful, mature way is essential for success in life outside the classroom. Additionally, Yussif (2023) also emphasized that respecting and acknowledging your students helps

to build bridges and creates a positive environment for learning. He expressed that respect begins with listening intently and not interrupting. It extends to treating others with dignity and respect, even if they make mistakes. Finally, it involves treating others as you would want to be treated.

3.2.2. Diversifying the lesson plan—It is significant that a teacher in a multicultural classroom is flexible with his/her lesson design. Similar to his/her students, there should also be variety in order to accommodate every student. One way of doing this is by integrating diversity into their lesson plan. In connection with the participants' responses, it can be inferred that the classroom environment is important for fostering cultural awareness, but one also should ensure diversity is represented in your actual lesson plan. An example was provided by Drexel University (2016). For example, broaden history lessons so that they encompass the world beyond the United States' history and culture. One may also use references and analogies to other cultures in your lessons and assignments to help students with diverse backgrounds personally connect. Another great strategy is bringing in diverse speakers to add varying points of view and real-life context to different subjects.

All these coincide with the teachers' strategies in how they deal with diversity in their multicultural classrooms. Furthermore, it was also stated that there are several ways you can in-grain cultural awareness and diversity into your lesson plan, and it will vary depending on the cultures represented in your classroom and the course you're teaching. Regardless of the subject, always try to present and connect lessons to real-world issues. It's easier to promote cultural awareness within your lessons when there's a real example for students to relate to. The extracted statements found further support from Khare (2018). He stated that inclusive classrooms have learners with a wide range of abilities. When we write goals that challenge students while at the same time, using effective scaffolding strategies to guide them when they struggle, we are able to challenge all learners in their own way. The flexibility in the goal allows us to do this.

3.3. Insights on the experiences of elementary school teachers—It is high time that we encourage inclusivity in the classroom. Multicultural education has evolved over time. Students managed to learn together despite the differences and teachers have been able to accom-

modate students from diverse backgrounds. The last research question of this study was to gather insights from the experiences and strategies of elementary school teachers in a multicultural classroom. The themes were formulated based on their responses.

3.3.1. Practicing cultural sensitivity—We have entered a time where society no longer lets differences create gaps, instead, differences are now acknowledged and respected. In a classroom, the teacher encounters students

who come from different backgrounds, bearing different cultures and values. They are also the ones that are tasked to make sure that every student feels welcomed and appreciated. Ang (2020) defines cultural sensitivity as be-

Fig. 4. Dealing with Diversity in a Multicultural Classroom

ing aware of cultural differences and similarities without evaluating these as good or bad. In line with the participant’s responses, they have stated the word respect. The term respect umbrella is the thought of being aware of the differences but not judging based on them. Cultural competence entails possessing the knowledge and skills required to manage cross-cultural relationships effectively. Meanwhile, Biode (2010) also agrees with the narratives. While it’s important to keep an open dialogue amongst students, it’s equally as important to make sure you’re being sensitive to everyone’s culture, beliefs, and language concerns. It is also important to take the time to understand each student’s cultural nuances – from learning styles to the language they use – and use these insights to design your lesson plans. The same study provided an ex-

ample to better understand the importance of cultural sensitivity in a multicultural classroom. English language learners with appropriate and relevant resources that help them improve their English comprehension skills. Rather than teach with a traditional lecture style, create learning experiences that are more interactive and require collaboration. These considerations will help ensure that every student feels included, is given the space to learn in their own way, and is given a chance to succeed. As one participant shared, rather than dwelling on what are the differences that are present in a classroom, a teacher should think of ways in which these differences can be acknowledged and respected. It will open doors and windows for more understanding while creating connections and relationships among students.

3.3.2. *Promote the value of learning about different cultures*—The classroom is a great place to stimulate discussions of various perspectives and for students to grow up appreci-

ating and normalizing collaboration with those who come from different backgrounds, have different values, and bring diverse perspectives. While some appreciation of diversity will hap-

pen organically based on exposure, teachers should still foster discussion and learn on the topic of diversity recognition. In light of the participants' narratives, Angelou (2020) supported their statements. According to her, learning about different cultures, ethnicities, and backgrounds is exciting and fun. No matter the ages of your students or what subject you teach, make an effort to expose your students to the value of different perspectives. This may include assigning readings from authors of diverse backgrounds, incorporating sociological considerations in your history classes, and highlighting the contributions of scientists and mathematicians from different countries and backgrounds. When students can see the unique contributions of people who differ from them, they may develop a deeper appreciation of diversity. It was further supported by Yussif (2023), who expressed that a classroom can be a safe place where everyone's opinions and experiences matter. Foster a culture of openness and acceptance in your classroom. Encourage students to talk about their backgrounds and cultures and show enthusiasm and interest in their contributions. Your students will follow your lead and may

develop a natural curiosity and interest in their classmates' experiences themselves. Moreover, appreciation for diversity should include an understanding and appreciation of one's own culture. The teacher should encourage students to research and learn about their heritage. It can be done by asking them to write a biography about an ancestor, explore the history of when their family first, or research an element about their culture, such as food, dance, or music (Ertac, 2018). To synthesize the results and discussion of the study, various themes were discovered during the conduct of the in-depth interview and focus group discussion of 10 elementary school teachers. The experiences of teachers in a multicultural classroom include students who have different socio-economic statuses, various learning styles, and differences in values among students. Meanwhile, in terms of strategies, it involved acknowledging and encouraging the students and diversifying the lesson plan. Finally, the insights gathered are promoting and practicing cultural sensitivity and the value of learning about different cultures. The discussion of all of these themes is supplemented by relevant pieces of literature.

4. Implications and Future Directions

This chapter presents the study summary, Implications, and Future Directions. I draw the implications and future directions from the summary of the findings. The purpose of my study was to discover the discourses of elementary school teachers regarding their experiences, strategies, and insights as they dealt with the challenges surrounding multicultural education. To achieve the research objectives, I made use of a qualitative phenomenological method with the use of thematic analysis. In adherence to Cresswell's (2006) guidelines open-ended questions for interviews were applied to get an authentic understanding of people's experiences. Furthermore, through this interview approach, I encouraged my participants to discuss their own definition or meaning of the phenomenon being explored which were the narratives of elementary school teachers fully and openly in a multicultural classroom. Taking into account the experiences shared by elementary school teachers in the in-depth interview and focus group discussion, three themes are identified. The first one is the presence of students with different socio-economic status. The participants have shared that the most common differences in their class are the student's socio-economic backgrounds. Some students have a lot while others barely have enough. However, they emphasized students coming from low-income backgrounds and how can pose disadvantages in a

Fig. 5. Insights on the Experiences of Elementary School Teachers in a Multicultural Classroom

student's learning. Hence, the teacher takes that factor into consideration, especially with tasks they assign to the students. The second theme was students with various learning styles. Students do not come in a box or in a certain shape and size; they come in different styles. One example was their learning styles. The participants acknowledged this difference among their students and made sure that no one in the class was left behind. They employed varied and flexible lesson designs to accommodate various learning styles. The last theme for the teachers' experiences was the differences in the attitudes and values of students. It was more likely that students in a multicultural classroom displayed different attitudes and values. It was mainly caused by their diverse background, different upbringings, and different perspectives they grew up with. However, teachers, do not let this difference cause conflicts and create gaps among their students, but they try to be as understanding and open-minded as possible. With regard to the strategies for dealing with diversity, two themes have been identified. First, acknowledging and encouraging every student. It was inevitable that the students may feel distant towards their classmates and even their teachers because of their differences. As a strategy, the participants opened up about acknowledging and encouraging their students. Acknowledging their difference instead of being embarrassed about them and encouraging them to speak and share about themselves while maintaining a safe and open discussion. Second, diversify the lesson plan. The participants shared that their students come in various shapes and sizes and are different in more ways than one. One way they could address this was by diversifying their lesson plan. They also integrate diversity in their activities so that they fit the student's needs. The final aim of the study was to gain insights from the elementary school teachers' experiences. The study discovered two themes. The first theme was practicing cultural sensitivity. The participants expressed that they still have a lot of learning to do regarding their students' backgrounds and cultures. They exerted effort to learn and understand more. Along with that, they practiced cultural sensitivity and open-mindedness; it was their way of respecting their students who come from diverse cultures. The second theme for the insights was promoting the value of learning about different cultures. As a teacher, they may encourage their students to appreciate and respect people who are different from them in various ways. Instead of judging, students should respect other culture or their classmates who are from different backgrounds. With learning comes understanding, and understanding is followed by respect.

4.1. Findings—Based on the results of the thematic analysis of the responses from the participants of the study, the following findings, and their corresponding themes were revealed: the experiences of elementary school teachers in a multicultural classroom include different socio-economic status, various learning styles and differences in attitudes and values of students. The strategies of teachers in dealing with diversity were acknowledging and encouraging every student and diversifying the lesson plan. The insights drawn from the findings of the study were: practicing cultural sensitivity and promoting the value of learning about different cultures.

4.2. Implications—The results of my analysis revealed the following significant findings. Every person was born into a culture that provides him with certain patterns of values and behaviors that serve as a guide in his life. Being aware of different cultures could help an individual better understand a person and adjust to their way of life in order to build a smooth

and harmonious relationship. One way of ensuring that people co-exist harmoniously despite individual differences was through education. One becomes well-informed, aware, and mindful of the appropriate conduct that is suitable to a certain culture. It also serves as a gateway to building respect among other people who come from diverse backgrounds and various upbringings and carry with them different perspectives. Education and culture were connected integrally and intimately since society's cultural pattern specifies its educational pattern. We are now in a time when our society practices and values inclusivity. This has opened doors and windows of opportunities to widen our perspectives and understanding. In this study, inclusivity is practiced in education. Every student everywhere, coming from different backgrounds and cultures, was welcomed and treated with equality. It connotes a positive message, and it symbolizes that we are taking the right path as a society. However, diversity in the classroom comes with challenges. Multicultural classrooms turn differences into chances to build connections and relationships. This study found that teachers' experiences in a multicultural classroom include students from different socio-economic statuses. This was one aspect that a teacher must consider because not all students have access to the same number of resources. Another experience is students' varied learning styles. Teachers, as the facilitators

of learning in the class, must make sure that the students learn in the best way possible in ways that suit their learning styles. Although it was a challenging undertaking, the teachers could be flexible and versatile with their activities so that they cater to the student's needs. Teachers also experienced students with different attitudes and values. Considering that students come from diverse backgrounds and cultures, it was more likely that they had different perspectives, views, and opinions regarding certain topics. However, amidst all the experiences and challenges that the teachers have encountered, they have come up with ways in order to deal with diversity in their classrooms. This includes acknowledging and encouraging every student to look at the brighter side of things. Instead of being disheartened by the differences, they should look at it as an opportunity to learn more. Another was by diversifying their lesson plan. This could make the students more engaged, active, and interested in the lesson. For the insights, teachers practice cultural diversity and have shown and promoted to students the value of learning about different cultures. From this study and based on the participants' narratives, it was essential to develop an understanding and respect for students with different backgrounds and cultures. Also, to those people who were different from us in various aspects. One should also make an effort to learn to be able to understand more.

4.3. Future Directions—Based on the findings of the study, it was important that the findings were properly relayed and used by the significant people whom this research was intended for. The Department of Education. The findings of this study may be helpful to the Department of Education in that they would give them an idea regarding the experiences of teachers in a multicultural classroom. They can also see how far multicultural education has come

and formulate ways and programs to further enhance and improve it. They could also provide support and assistance to teachers, such as diverse teaching materials for their multicultural classrooms. The school principals/school heads may be more proactive and supportive in implementing multicultural education, especially in schools with students from various ethnic tribes and diverse cultural backgrounds. They may also devise programs to provide assistance

for students from low-income backgrounds so that it does not hinder their education. Other stakeholders may provide support to enhance the teaching-learning experience in a multicultural classroom and may be the source of other ways and means to solve some of the challenges faced by teachers. The teachers may be more informed and aware of the differences present in their classrooms. Acknowledging these differences can help them understand their students better and allow them to contextualize their lessons and discussions, which would encourage more student engagement and participation. The future researchers. They may conduct the study but take the perspective of the students who are in multicultural classrooms. Focusing on their experiences and challenges faced by being in a diverse class with diverse classmates and if the strategies employed by the teachers were deemed effective in a multicultural classroom. They may also explore different challenges and strategies to open good and new avenues to improve the way learners learn.

5. References

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